

Feasibility Study of POD Tallies for the Coupled Simulation with a Single Fuel Assembly

Ryoichi Kondo^{1,2*}, Carren Liang², Akio Yamamoto², Tomohiro Endo²

¹ Japan Atomic Energy Agency, 2-4 Shirakata, Tokai-mura, Naka-gun, Ibaraki, Japan;

² Nagoya University, Furo-cho, Chikusa-ku, Nagoya, Aichi, Japan;

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803966

ABSTRACT

We developed distribution tallies with proper orthogonal decomposition, referred to as POD tallies, to address the issues of high-fidelity Monte Carlo calculations. The advantages of the POD tallies are the reduction of dimensionality and statistical error. The distribution quantity is expanded by orthogonal basis vectors. As a feasibility study for multi-physics simulation, the POD tallies are applied to the three-dimensional fission reaction rate of a BWR single fuel assembly of a coupled simulation with a thermal-hydraulics calculation. The pre-calculated coupled simulation performed by the GenesisRPC code for the neutronics calculation and ACE-3D for the thermal-hydraulics calculation is used. The three-dimensional POD tallies are performed with a multi-group Monte Carlo code GMVP. The target distribution is the distribution in the converged state of the iteration on the coupled simulation. The distribution in the un-converged state of the iteration is used as snapshots to extract the POD basis vectors. The fission reaction rate distribution reconstructed by the POD tallies with a fourth-order expansion agrees with that of the cell tallies within the statistical error. The dimensionality is reduced by a factor of 16. The systematic error is not observed in each radial distribution. This result indicates that the POD basis vectors extracted from the distribution in the un-converged state can expand that in the converged state. Through the dimensionality reduction, the statistical error, defined as l^2 -norm based standard deviation is reduced by approximately half.

Keywords: Monte Carlo method, distribution tallies, proper orthogonal decomposition, POD tallies, coupled simulation

1. INTRODUCTION

Although computational capabilities have significantly advanced in recent years, high-fidelity multi-physics simulations for nuclear reactors still require substantial computational resources. For neutronics calculations, the Monte Carlo method is widely employed due to its accuracy [1,2], solving the neutron transport calculation without discretization of phase space. In multi-physics simulations, the neutronics calculation code provides flux and power distributions to thermal-hydraulic and fuel performance codes. However, due to the nature of the MC method, maintaining statistical accuracy requires increasingly more computational resources as the resolution of the distribution increases.

To address the challenges in obtaining distribution quantities, functional expansion tallies (FETs) [3] have traditionally been employed in multi-physics simulations [4]. FETs have the advantage of providing continuous distributions. However, the use of analytical orthogonal polynomials, i.e., Legendre and Zernike polynomials, limits the applicable geometries. As an alternative approach, we have developed distribution tallies using proper orthogonal decomposition (POD), referred to as POD tallies [5,6]. In POD tallies, the target distribution is represented as a linear combination of orthogonal basis vectors. POD basis vectors are extracted from pre-calculated snapshot data obtained by the deterministic method through singular value decomposition (SVD). The expansion coefficient corresponding to the POD basis vectors is tallied during the MC calculation. The dimensionality of the

*kondo.ryoichi@jaea.go.jp

solution is reduced from the number of spatial meshes in the distribution to the number of expansion coefficients. In conventional cell tallies, a quantity is scored for each mesh when a particle enters the mesh. Therefore, the statistical error becomes large when the number of mesh increases. In the POD tallies, the weights corresponding to the POD basis vectors are scored when a particle enters the expanded region, e.g., a fuel assembly region. Since the particle contributes to the entire region, the reduction of statistical error can be achieved. In the previous study, the POD tallies were verified for a two-dimensional problem [6].

This study aims to investigate the applicability of POD tallies to a three-dimensional fission rate distribution in a coupled simulation with the thermal-hydraulics calculation. As a feasibility study, a single assembly of boiling water reactors (BWRs) is used. The target distribution is the converged result obtained from the iterations of neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations. A distribution in the un-converged state is used for snapshot data. The reconstructed distribution is compared with the conventional cell tallies.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes an overview of the POD tallies and an approach to generate the POD basis vectors for a three-dimensional BWR single fuel assembly. Section 3 presents the calculation results. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the present work and future challenges.

2. METHOD

2.1. Overview of the POD Tallies

A target spatial distribution of the fission reaction rate \vec{F} with R meshes is expressed as a linear combination of the POD basis vectors as follows:

$$\vec{F} = \mathbf{U}\vec{a} = a_1\vec{u}_1 + a_2\vec{u}_2 + \dots + a_N\vec{u}_N, \quad (1)$$

where a_n and \vec{u}_n are the n -th expansion coefficient and POD basis vector. The expansion coefficient can be written as follows:

$$a_n = \vec{u}_n^T \cdot \vec{F} = \sum_{r=1}^R u_{n,r} F_r, \quad (2)$$

where $u_{n,r}$ the element of the n -th expansion coefficient at mesh r . The fission reaction rate at mesh r is tallied by the track-length estimator as follows:

$$F_r = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{p=1}^{P_h} \Sigma_{f,r} w_{r,h,p} d_{r,h,p}, \quad (3)$$

where h and p are the indices of history and path length, respectively; H and P_h are the number of histories and path length, respectively; $\Sigma_{f,r}$, $w_{r,h,p}$ and $d_{r,h,p}$ are the macroscopic fission reaction cross section, the weight of the history, and the path length. By substituting Eq. (3) into Eq. (2), the expansion coefficient is tallied as follows:

$$a_n = \vec{u}_n^T \cdot \vec{F} = \sum_{r=1}^R \left(u_{n,r} \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{p=1}^{P_h} \Sigma_{f,r} w_{r,h,p} d_{r,h,p} \right) = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H \left(\sum_{r=1}^R \left(\sum_{p=1}^{P_h} u_{n,r} \Sigma_{f,r} w_{r,h,p} d_{r,h,p} \right) \right). \quad (4)$$

The target distribution is reconstructed by Eq. (1) once the expansion coefficients are obtained in the MC calculation. The dimensionality is reduced from the number of meshes R to the number of expansion coefficients N .

2.2. Generation of POD Basis Vectors for a Three-Dimensional Single Assembly

A target distribution is the pin-by-pin three-dimensional fission reaction rate of a BWR fuel assembly. The number of meshes is $R_{xy} \times R_z$, where R_{xy} and R_z are the number of radial meshes, i.e., the number of fuel pins, and the number of axial mesh divisions in an assembly, respectively. In the present study, a two-dimensional radial distribution in each axial mesh is expanded by the POD basis vectors. Therefore, two-dimensional POD basis vectors are prepared. Snapshots are two-dimensional radial distributions in an axial mesh in the three-dimensional distribution with one or multiple calculation conditions. A snapshot matrix is constructed as follows:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{F}_{1,1} & \dots & \vec{F}_{1,R_z} & \vec{F}_{2,1} & \dots & \vec{F}_{2,R_z} & \dots & \vec{F}_{NC,1} & \dots & \vec{F}_{NC,R_z} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} F_{1,1,1} & \dots & F_{1,R_z,1} & F_{2,1,1} & \dots & F_{2,R_z,1} & \dots & F_{NC,1,1} & \dots & F_{NC,R_z,1} \\ \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ F_{1,1,R_{xy}} & \dots & F_{1,R_z,R_{xy}} & F_{2,1,R_{xy}} & \dots & F_{2,R_z,R_{xy}} & \dots & F_{NC,1,R_{xy}} & \dots & F_{NC,R_z,R_{xy}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $F_{nc,r_z,r_{xy}}$ is the snapshot fission reaction rate at mesh (r_z, r_{xy}) in the nc -th calculation condition. Note that the number of calculation conditions NC should be small since performing a large number of three-dimensional snapshot calculations is impractical. A three-dimensional POD basis vector might be generated from three-dimensional snapshots. However, the existing approach by preparing the snapshots, e.g., perturbing albedo values [6], requires large computational resources. By arranging radial distributions, the solution space expressing the target distribution can be extended with fewer snapshot calculations. The POD basis vectors \mathbf{U} are extracted by singular value decomposition (SVD) as follows:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T. \quad (6)$$

In the present study, the fission reaction rate distribution obtained in a coupled simulation before convergence is used as a snapshot. All radial distributions in the target three-dimensional distribution are expanded with the same POD basis vectors.

3. CALCULATION

3.1. Calculation Conditions

For the feasibility study of the POD tallies, the pre-calculated results of the coupled simulation conducted with neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations are used [7]. The coupled simulation was conducted with a simplified BWR single fuel assembly based on OECD/NEA Benchmark Phase III B [8], shown in Figure 1. A fuel lattice consists of 8×8 fuel rods without water rod and, surrounded by a 0.25-cm-thick channel box. Pitch of a fuel cell, radius of fuel pellet, and radius of cladding are 1.63 cm, 0.529 cm, and 0.615 cm, respectively. The fuel composition is 1.63 wt% UO_2 . The cladding and the channel box consist of Zircaloy. The temperature, pressure, and velocity of the inlet water are 549.3 K, 7.07 MPa, and 2.15 m/s, respectively. The total power of the assembly is 4.6 MW. Neutronics is calculated with a general neutronics analysis code GenesisRPC [9], developed based on the Genesis code [10] with the method of characteristics (MOC). The three-dimensional problem is solved by the LEAF method [11]. The GenesisRPC processes GENDF (Groupwise-ENDF) and calculates effective cross sections. The 70 multi-group cross section from JENDL-5 [12] is used. The fuel region and the water reflector regions (top and bottom) are equally divided into 24 and 2 meshes, respectively. The temperature of the fuel, cladding, channel box, and water reflector is constant. The temperature and density of water in each cell of the lattice region are updated by the results of the thermal-hydraulics code ACE-3D [13], based on a three-dimensional two-fluid model. Details can be found in the reference [7]. The coupled simulation is performed with five iterations, starting from the neutronics calculation. The pin-by-pin fission reaction rate distributions are obtained from the GenesisRPC. The distribution converges at the fifth iteration, as shown in the axial distribution in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Geometry of a BWR single fuel assembly.

Figure 2. Fission reaction rate distribution obtained from GenesisRPC.

The verification of the POD tallies is conducted in the calculation condition of the fifth iteration. A multi-group MC calculation is performed with a multi-group MC code GMVP [14]. The 70 group cross section, considering P_2 anisotropic scattering obtained from the GenesisRPC calculation, is used for each axial mesh. The GMVP code is modified to output fission reaction rate distribution for each batch. Since the MC algorithm is not modified, the memory consumption does not change. A POD expansion coefficient for each batch is calculated by Eq. (2). By statistically processing the POD expansion coefficients for each batch, the POD expansion coefficients for the eigenvalue calculation are consequently obtained. In the present study, the fission reaction rate distributions of the cell and POD tallies are obtained from one MC calculation with track-length estimator. The MC calculation is performed with the following conditions: the number of histories per batch, active batches, and inactive batches are 400,000, 400, and 160, respectively. The standard deviation of the fission reaction rate obtained by the cell tallies is $\sim 0.3\%$ as a root mean square of all meshes.

The snapshot is required to generate POD basis vectors. The fission reaction rate distribution at the second iteration obtained from the GenesisRPC calculation is chosen as the snapshot since the feedback effect of the thermal-hydraulics calculation is included. As described in Section 2.2, the POD basis vectors for radial distribution are generated. The size of the snapshot matrix is 24×64 since NC , R_z , and R_{xy} are 1, 24, and 64, respectively. The 24 POD basis vectors are extracted by SVD.

3.2. Numerical Results

The trend of the singular values obtained from the snapshots is shown in Figure 3. The values are relative values for singular values of the first order. The magnitude of the singular value indicates the contribution of the corresponding POD basis vector to the snapshots. The singular value decreases exponentially. Since the order of the residual error in scalar flux with the MOC is 10^{-4} , the basis vectors up to the fifth, with magnitudes of $\sim 10^{-5}$, can be effective for reconstruction.

Figure 3. Singular value obtained from the snapshot of the fission reaction rate distribution.

The trend of the POD basis vectors is shown in Figure 4. The radial distributions of the POD basis vectors appear in order of importance based on the magnitude of the corresponding singular value. The first to ninth POD basis vectors are point-symmetric distribution, capturing the entire radial distribution of the fission reaction rate. Since the calculation condition of the snapshot is point-symmetric distribution in radial direction, the POD basis vectors from first to ninth are important. The POD basis vectors after the ninth would capture the residual error of the convergence in the MOC. Additionally, the numerical calculation of SVD could cause noise. The trend of the POD basis vectors indicates that the lower order bases could be effective for the target distribution.

Figure 4. Singular value obtained from the snapshot of the fission reaction rate distribution.

The results of the MC calculation are described in the following. The difference of the three-dimensional fission reaction rate distribution between the cell and POD tallies is shown in Figure 5, as root mean

square error (RMSE) with respect to the POD expansion order. Two-dimensional radial distributions of all axial positions are expanded with the same number of POD basis vectors. The RMSE converges at the fourth order by $\sim 0.3\%$. Since the cell tallies have $\sim 0.3\%$ statistical error as the root mean square of all meshes, the POD tallies with the fourth-order expansion have enough accuracy. The dimensionality of each radial distribution is reduced from $64=8 \times 8$ (the number of meshes) to 4 (the number of expansion coefficients).

Figure 5. The difference of the three-dimensional fission reaction rate distribution between the cell and POD tallies as root mean square error with respect to the POD expansion order.

Figure 6 shows the relative differences between the POD with the fourth-order expansion and cell tallies of the fission reaction rate at the axial positions. The bottom, top, and the 6th axial mesh, where the fission reaction rate has a peak, are shown as representative. The distribution shows random fluctuations, and the systematic differences are not observed. Since both the cell and POD tallies have statistical errors, the cause of the differences might be the statistical error of the MC calculations. Therefore, the POD tallies reconstruct the results of the cell tallies within the statistical error. This result indicates that the POD basis vectors extracted from the distribution of the second iteration before convergence can expand the converged state of the fifth iteration.

Figure 6. Relative difference of the fission reaction rate distribution at the axial positions.

The l^2 -norm based standard deviation, defined as the root mean square of standard deviation over all meshes, is obtained to evaluate the statistical error. The l^2 -norm based standard deviations of the POD and cell tallies are shown in Figure 7. Since the POD tallies show enough accuracy at fourth-order expansion as described above, the statistical error is reduced by approximately half compared with the cell tallies as l^2 -norm based standard deviation. This reduction in statistical error theoretically corresponds to a fourfold increase in computation time.

Figure 7. Statistical error as l^2 -norm based standard deviation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The POD tallies were applied to the three-dimensional fission reaction rate distribution of the BWR single fuel assembly obtained in the coupled simulation. The radial two-dimensional distribution at each axial position was expanded by the POD basis vectors. The snapshot matrix consisted of radial distributions in the three-dimensional distribution. The target distribution was the fission reaction rate in the converged state of the fifth iteration. The snapshot was the distribution of the un-converged state of the second iteration. The results of the POD tallies with fourth-order expansion agreed with those of the cell tallies within the statistical error. This result indicated that the POD basis vectors extracted from the distribution of the un-converged state can expand the distribution of the converged state. The dimensionality was reduced by a factor of 16. Consequently, the statistical error, defined as l^2 -norm based standard deviation was reduced by approximately half.

The remaining issues are as follows. Firstly, the snapshot preparation of the present study is applied to the different conditions. For example, an assembly with partially inserted control rods or multiple assemblies would be a challenging issue. Secondly, a more efficient snapshot generation should be investigated. In the present study, snapshots were constructed from three-dimensional neutronics calculations considering thermal-hydraulic feedback explicitly. Alternatively, snapshots could be generated from two-dimensional neutronics calculations with varying void fractions or temperatures. Evaluating the accuracy of the POD basis vectors, as well as investigating the overall computation cost, remains an important subject. Finally, the implementation of the POD tallies to a continuous energy MC calculation. Because the deterministic method is used for snapshot calculations, the impact of the energy discretization of the snapshot is investigated.

REFERENCES

1. T. KAMIYA *et al.*, "Neutronics/Thermal-Hydraulics Coupling Simulation Using JAMPAN in a Single BWR Assembly," *Mech. Eng. J.*, **vol. 12**, no. 4, pp. 24–00461, 2025, doi: 10.1299/mej.24-00461.
2. T. Albagami, P. Rouxelin, A. Abarca, S. Palmtag, M. Avramova, and K. Ivanov, "Development of Serpent/CTF External Coupling for the OECD/NEA TVA-WB1 Benchmark Activities," *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, Apr. 2025, doi: 10.1080/00295639.2025.2475415.
3. D. P. Griesheimer, W. R. Martin, and J. P. Holloway, "Estimation of Flux Distributions with Monte Carlo Functional Expansion Tallies," *Radiat. Prot. Dosimetry*, **vol. 115**, no. 1–4, pp. 428–432, Dec. 2005, doi: 10.1093/rpd/nci265.
4. M. Ellis, D. Gaston, B. Forget, and K. Smith, "Preliminary Coupling of the Monte Carlo Code OpenMC and the Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment for Analyzing Doppler Feedback in Monte Carlo Simulations," *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **vol. 185**, no. 1, pp. 184–193, 2017, doi: 10.13182/NSE16-26.

5. R. Kondo, T. Endo, and A. Yamamoto, "Flux Distribution Tallies Using Proper Orthogonal Decomposition in Monte Carlo Calculations," *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **vol. 61**, no. 12, pp. 1536–1545, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1080/00223131.2024.2365445.
6. R. Kondo, A. Yamamoto, and T. Endo, "Sub-pin Level Distribution Tallies and Statistical Error Estimation with POD Tallies in Two-Dimensional C5G7 Benchmark," *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, Sep. 2025, doi: 10.1080/00223131.2025.2554969.
7. C. Liong, T. Kenichi, T. Endo, "Prediction of Coolant Void Fraction and Temperature Distributions by Deep Neural Network in Coupled Multi-Physics Simulation of Boiling Water Reactor 8×8 Pin Bundle," *Proc. PHYSOR2026*, Torino, Italy, Apr. 19–23, 2026.
8. O., Hiroshi, N. Yoshitaka, and S. Kenya, "OECD/NEA Burnup Credit Criticality Benchmarks Phase IIIB; Burnup Calculations of BWR Fuel Assemblies for Storage and Transport," JAERI, Tokai, Ibaraki, Japan, JAERI-Research 2002-001, Feb. 2002, doi: 10.11484/jaeri-research-2002-001.
9. A. Yamamoto, T. Endo, and T. Watanabe, "Effects of Self-shielding and Scattering Matrix Treatments in Detailed Burnup Calculation," *Trans. Am. Nucl. Soc.*, **vol. 133**, Nov. 2025, pp. 698–701.
10. A. Yamamoto, A. Giho, Y. Kato, and T. Endo, "GENESIS: A Three-Dimensional Heterogeneous Transport Solver Based on the Legendre Polynomial Expansion of Angular Flux Method," *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **vol. 186**, no. 1, pp. 1–22, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.1080/00295639.2016.1273002.
11. A. Giho, K. Sakai, Y. Imamura, H. Sakuragi, and K. Miyawaki, "Development of Axially Simplified Method of Characteristics in Three-Dimensional Geometry," *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **vol. 45**, no. 10, pp. 985–996, Oct. 2008, doi: 10.1080/18811248.2008.9711884.
12. O. Iwamoto *et al.*, "Japanese Evaluated Nuclear Data Library Version 5: JENDL-5," *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **vol. 60**, no. 1, pp. 1–60, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1080/00223131.2022.2141903.
13. A. Ohnuki, H. Kamo, H. Akimoto, "Improvement of Multi-dimensional Two-Fluid Model Code ACE3D and Application to Thermal-Hydraulic Analysis of Water Pool for Passive Residual Heat Removal," JAERI, Tokai, Ibaraki, Japan, JAERI-Data/Code 99-038, Aug. 1999, doi: 10.11484/jaeri-data-code-99-038.
14. Y. Nagaya, K. Okumura, T. Sakurai, and T. Mori, "MVP/GMVP Version 3: General Purpose Monte Carlo Codes for Neutron and Photon Transport Calculations Based on Continuous Energy and Multigroup Methods," JAEA, Tokai, Ibaraki, Japan, JAEA-Data/Code, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.11484/jaea-data-code-2016-018.